

Figure Z19

Figure Z19: Cross-tissue communication at cell-state level. Cross-tissue ligand-receptor networks across tissue pairs (row panels) in the four intervention groups (column panels). Number of interactions (heatmaps) between source-tissue cell states with ligand (rows) and target-tissue cell states with interacting receptors (columns) are plotted. Cell-state pairs with relatively higher number of interactions in each heatmap are highlighted using red rectangles. A list of abbreviations used in this figure appear in the Methods.